

Supplementary File 1. Complete Search Strategy

Title of the review

Effectiveness of Physical Activity Interventions on Mental Health Outcomes among Natural Disaster Survivors: A Systematic Review of Proximal and Complex Effects

Search Information

- **Databases searched:** Scopus and PubMed
- **Search date:** February 2026
- **Language restriction:** English
- **Publication type:** Journal articles
- **Time period:** 2015-2026
- **Search performed by:** Widia Aningsih

Database 1. Scopus

Platform: Scopus

Date searched: February 2026

Search query:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("disaster survivor*" OR "natural disaster*" OR earthquake OR flood OR tsunami OR "post-disaster") AND ("exercise intervention" OR "physical activity" OR "training program" OR "sport" OR "structured exercise") AND ("mental health" OR "psychological well-being" OR "self-esteem" OR resilience OR depression OR anxiety))

Filter applied

- Language: English
- Publication years: 2015-2026
- Document type: Article

Records retrieved: 394

Database 2. PubMed

Platform: PubMed

Date searched: February 2026

Search query

((("Disasters"[MeSH] OR "disaster survivor*" OR "natural disaster*" OR earthquake OR flood OR tsunami OR "post-disaster")) AND (("Exercise"[MeSH] OR "Motor Activity"[MeSH] OR "physical activity" OR "exercise intervention" OR "training program" OR sport OR "structured exercise")) AND (("Mental Health"[MeSH] OR "psychological well-being" OR "self-esteem" OR resilience OR depression OR anxiety)) AND (("Randomized Controlled Trial"[Publication Type] OR "controlled trial" OR "experimental study" OR intervention))

Filters applied

- Language: English
- Publication years: 2015-2026

Records retrieved: 28

Summary of Search Results

Database	Records Retrieved
Scopus	394
PubMed	28
Total	422

Notes

Duplicate records identified during database merging were removed before title and abstract screening. The screening process was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidelines.